

Gaze and Language in Action: Multimodal Interfaces for Cognitive Assistance

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Abstract. In this paper, we present a novel software framework for portable, gaze-aware assistance, aimed at supporting people with dementia during daily kitchen tasks. Unlike traditional systems that rely on fixed infrastructure, our approach enables real-time, context-sensitive guidance using a host device (e.g., a laptop) together with Meta’s Project Aria smart glasses. The core contribution lies in a multimodal sensor fusion architecture that combines egocentric vision (YOLOv8n-based object detection), binocular gaze tracking, and inertial spatial localisation. This fusion supports persistent object awareness without requiring environmental instrumentation. Detected objects and their spatial context are structured into a knowledge graph (KG) that maps feasible user actions. A compact language model (GPT-4o-mini) leverages this representation to generate voice-based task prompts, such as reminders to turn off the stove, instructions to make tea, or explanations about kitchen items. All assistance is delivered through non-intrusive voice feedback. Preliminary evaluations indicate the feasibility of this approach for enabling lightweight, wearable, and adaptive support in unstructured indoor environments for cognitively impaired users.

Keywords: Dementia Support · Smart Glasses · Computer Vision.

1 Context and Contribution

Dementia affects an estimated 57.4M people worldwide and may reach 152.8M by 2050 [13]. Individuals with dementia often experience memory impairments, confusion, and difficulties in performing routine tasks, significantly reducing their independence and quality of life [3]. One daily task where this can pose particularly significant risks is cooking. Meanwhile, large language models (LLMs) have already demonstrated that they can assist in a range of tasks like writing, planning, and problem solving [16,2,17,18,22], and industrial wearables (e.g., RealWear Navigator 520) deliver hands-free guidance [15]; yet home deployments for cognitive decline remain rare and many assistive systems depend on fixed smart-home infrastructure [9,1]. Early dementia-focused wearables support recognition/navigation but lack fine-grained, kitchen-centric interaction [7,6].

Meta’s Project Aria provides first-person RGB, binocular gaze, inertial measurement unit (IMU), microphones, and GPS, and underpins major egocentric datasets/benchmarks [5,8,20,14]. Building on this, we introduce a portable

framework that fuses gaze, egocentric vision, and inertial data to deliver spatially grounded, voice-only guidance *without* requiring environmental instrumentation. Detected objects and their layout populate a KG that constrains GPT-4o-mini to generate concise, context-aware prompts aligned with what is feasible *now*. Our contributions are: (1) a multimodal fusion stack enabling persistent object awareness on commodity hardware; (2) KG-constrained language suggestions grounded in detected items and spatial context; and (3) a preliminary kitchen evaluation indicating real-time operation with promising component accuracy.

2 Methodology

The proposed system consists of four main components: (1) wearable sensing using Meta’s Project Aria smart glasses, (2) a host device for perception and inference, (3) a task reasoning module using a KG, and (4) a natural language suggestion interface powered by an LLM. Sensor data is streamed from the glasses to the host device, which processes the input to generate real-time spoken prompts. An overview of the system architecture is shown in Figure 1. As illustrated, the system comprises four primary data streams: an audio stream, an RGB video stream, an IMU data stream, and a monochrome eye video stream. Each stream is processed independently, and their outputs are ultimately fused to generate a spoken response based on the user’s query or current context. The implementation of the entire system is available on GitHub, where all the data used is either provided or appropriately linked, and there is a demo video of the whole system.¹

Fig. 1. System architecture of the proposed kitchen assistance platform using Meta’s Project Aria glasses. Glasses image adapted from [10].

2.1 System Hardware and Sensor Overview

The glasses provide four key sensor streams: a front-facing RGB camera, an IMU, two monochrome eye-tracking cameras, and a microphone. These sensors enable

¹ GitHub repository: <https://github.com/lokrau/GLAMICA>; demo video: <https://youtu.be/BfITB2UJyzU>.

object detection, spatial awareness, gaze estimation and sound recognition. All of these are essential for delivering personalised assistance in real time.

The sensor data is streamed to an external computing device for processing. This device is a laptop with an Apple M1 Pro processor, 16GB of RAM, 512GB of storage and a macOS Sequoia 15.5 operating system.

2.2 Perception Pipeline: Object Detection and Localisation

The system uses a combination of RGB camera data and inertial measurements from the Meta Project Aria glasses to perform object detection and spatial tracking. For the detection task, a YOLOv8n model was fine-tuned on a custom kitchen dataset. This model was selected for its balance of speed and accuracy on consumer-grade hardware.

The dataset consists of 837 annotated images containing 5,365 labelled instances across ten kitchen-relevant classes: *Stove*, *Faucet*, *Pot*, *Spoon*, *Plate*, *Cup*, *Hand*, *Pasta*, *Rice*, and *Tea*. Of these, 533 images were self-collected using Project Aria glasses and manually annotated. In addition, 300 images were sourced from [19], and four images were taken from [4]. All external images were reviewed for correctness and annotated to include the additional object classes required for this work. These external samples were added to reduce dataset bias toward the layout and appearance of the specific kitchen used during data collection. Data augmentation techniques—including rotation, brightness, exposure, and blur—were applied to enhance generalization. The dataset was split into 80% training, 10% validation, and 10% test data, and training was performed using the Ultralytics Python library.

To improve detection robustness, an object is only considered present if it appears in at least 10 consecutive frames with a confidence score above 40%. This temporal consistency filter reduces false positives due to brief occlusions or detection noise.

To enable object permanence and spatial awareness, the IMU is used to estimate the user’s head orientation. The system integrates gyroscopic angular velocity from an initial heading of 0 radians, and combines this with each object’s position in the image frame. A conversion factor of 0.038° per pixel is applied, based on Project Aria’s optical calibration data [11], to estimate the object’s direction relative to the user.

To mitigate IMU bias, a static baseline was recorded for one hour while the glasses were stationary on a table. Based on that a correction offset of 0.004757 rad/s was calculated as the average bias of the gyroscope used in the IMU (see Figure 2), since normally the sensor should read 0 all the time when stationary. This bias is subtracted during operation. Each object’s angular position θ_r relative to the user’s heading is then discretized into four directional zones:

$$Z(\theta_r) = \begin{cases} \text{“front”} & \text{if } -\frac{\pi}{4} \leq \theta_r < \frac{\pi}{4} \\ \text{“right”} & \text{if } \frac{\pi}{4} \leq \theta_r < \frac{3\pi}{4} \\ \text{“behind”} & \text{if } \theta_r \geq \frac{3\pi}{4} \text{ or } \theta_r < -\frac{3\pi}{4} \\ \text{“left”} & \text{if } -\frac{3\pi}{4} \leq \theta_r < -\frac{\pi}{4} \end{cases}$$

Fig. 2. IMU gyroscope bias while stationary on a table. Values averaged per second.

This combined approach allows the system to retain awareness of object locations even when they are no longer in view—crucial for assisting users with memory or attention impairments in dynamic environments like kitchens.

2.3 Gaze Estimation

The gaze estimation uses the monochrome eye video stream from the Project Aria glasses to estimate where the user is currently looking in the RGB video stream. For this, an open-source machine learning model developed by Meta is used [12]. The model takes the monochrome eye video stream as an input which contains both eyes of the user in one image of size 640x240 pixels. Based on this, the model outputs the estimated yaw and pitch angles of the user’s gaze in radians. These angles are then used to calculate the gaze point in the RGB video stream.

This gaze point in the RGB image is then combined with the detected items from the YOLOv8n model and their location in the frame. To determine the gaze target, we compare the gaze point with the YOLOv8n bounding boxes. The candidate whose center has the smallest angular distance to the gaze point is selected, provided this distance is $\leq 8^\circ$ (≈ 200 px using the $0.038^\circ/\text{px}$ calibration); otherwise no object is assigned.

The Aria glasses also offer the option to calibrate the monochrome eye cameras. Even though this increases the accuracy, it was chosen not to do this, to avoid the per-user setup burden.

2.4 Task Suggestion with LLM

To assist users with contextually appropriate meal guidance, the system integrates a generative LLM that produces natural language suggestions based on detected kitchen items and their spatial positions. This approach allows for open-ended, step-by-step instructions without the need for rigid rule-based logic.

After benchmarking several models for performance and system compatibility, two deployment strategies were compared: (1) running compact open-source models locally (SmolVLM-500M, TinyLlama, Phi-2, and Mistral-7B) using `llama.cpp`, and (2) accessing GPT-4o-mini via the OpenAI API. While Mistral-7B-Instruct v0.2 generated the most coherent responses locally, its inference latency on the target hardware (Subsection 2.1) was significantly higher than the API-based approach. Ultimately, GPT-4o-mini was selected for its superior response time and output quality.

To ensure that suggestions are grounded in the user’s current context, the system uses a KG that encodes common kitchen tasks as combinations of required objects. For instance, the task “make tea” is defined as requiring a combination of items such as a *Cup*, *Faucet*, *Tea*, *Pot*, *Spoon*, and *Stove*. The current KG supports four predefined kitchen tasks: *making a cup of water* (requires *Cup*, and *Faucet*), *making a cup of tea* (requires *Cup*, *Tea*, *Faucet*, *Stove*, *Pot*, and *Spoon*), *cooking pasta* (requires *Faucet*, *Stove*, *Pot*, *Spoon*, *Plate*, and *Pasta*), and *cooking rice* (requires *Faucet*, *Stove*, *Pot*, *Spoon*, *Plate*, *Cup* and *Rice*).

When a suggestion is triggered—either by button press or a spoken/typed prompt (see Table 1)—the system begins by compiling a list of all currently detected objects along with their spatial orientations (e.g., front, left). It then queries the KG to identify which predefined tasks are feasible based on the available objects. Simultaneously, it identifies the object currently being looked at using gaze tracking. This information—detected items, their directions, possible tasks, and gaze focus—is embedded into a structured prompt and sent to the language model, which generates a step-by-step suggestion tailored to both the user’s intent and the real-time environmental state.

This module transforms low-level object detection and gaze tracking into meaningful, personalized suggestions. It forms the central interaction layer of the system, providing cognitively appropriate guidance based on the environment.

2.5 Reactive Feedback: Action Recognition

Action recognition is a core component of the system, enabling it to provide context-aware feedback in response to user behavior. The current implementation focuses on recognizing two specific actions: turning the stove and the faucet on or off. These actions were selected because they represent significant safety risks in the context of kitchen activities. Leaving the stove on for an extended

Type	Template Text
Predefined Prompt (Button Trigger)	“Imagine I’m a person with dementia. Don’t mention that I have dementia. I have the following items with the information where they are right now, nothing else: [<i>Cup: front, Faucet: back, Tea: left</i>]. Given this and assuming only the following things are possible: [<i>cup of water</i>], can you give me steps for how to do only one of those listed things with the items I have? If the list of things that are possible states "none", tell me that nothing is possible to make.”
User Prompt (Typed/Spoken)	“The detected objects in my surroundings right now are: [<i>Cup: front, Faucet: back, Tea: left</i>]. With those items I can make this: [<i>cup of water</i>]. Besides of that, I am currently looking at: [<i>gaze target</i>]. Do not suggest anything else to me. [<i>user query</i>]”

Table 1. Prompt templates used for language model interaction based on user input modality.

period increases the risk of fire, while an unattended running faucet can waste water and potentially cause overflow and water damage.

Stove State Recognition Stove activation is detected through the spatial and temporal co-occurrence of hand and stove detections. The system assumes that the stove’s controls are located within the outer 20% of the stove’s bounding box. If a detected *Hand* bounding box overlaps with this control region continuously for at least 1.5 seconds, the stove’s state is toggled.

Once the system determines that the stove has been turned on, it issues a verbal reminder every minute to prompt user awareness:

“The stove has been turned on for [*time since turned on in minutes*] minute[s]. You should check on it.”

Faucet State Recognition To detect the state of the faucet, a dedicated machine learning model was developed using audio classification. A pre-trained YAMNet model was chosen for feature extraction due to its proven efficiency with audio data [21]. YAMNet produces a 1,024-dimensional embedding vector, which serves as input to a custom fully connected classifier.

The classifier architecture includes a fully connected layer with 128 neurons and ReLU activation, followed by a 30 percent dropout. This is followed by another fully connected layer with 64 neurons, again with ReLU activation and 30 percent dropout. The final layer uses Softmax activation with two output neurons corresponding to the classes *noise* and *faucet*.

The model was trained on a self-recorded dataset using the laptop described in Subsection 2.1 and the Project Aria glasses. The dataset includes 20 minutes and 4 seconds of *noise* and 20 minutes and 4 seconds of running *faucet* recordings, of which 10 minutes each have been recorded using the laptop and the rest using the Aria glasses. This decision has been made to generalise the model better to different microphones. After recording the data it was segmented into 602

two-second clips for each label. The data was split into 80% training, 10% test, and 10% validation sets.

The classifier runs continuously in the background, recording two-second audio segments and classifying them in real time. When the label *faucet* is predicted, the faucet state is set to on; when *noise* is detected, it is set to off. While the faucet is active, the system issues a verbal reminder every 10 seconds:

“The faucet has been turned on for a bit. You should check on it.”

This action recognition module is designed to reduce safety risks associated with unattended appliances, a common concern for individuals with dementia.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Deploying assistive technologies for cognitively impaired individuals raises critical concerns around privacy, safety, and autonomy. To preserve user confidentiality, all raw sensor data—such as video, audio, and gaze streams—is processed locally on the host device. The only data transmitted to external services (e.g., the OpenAI API) is fully anonymized and abstracted: it includes only a symbolic list of detected objects, their spatial orientations (e.g., “cup: left”), the object currently being looked at, and which predefined kitchen tasks are feasible. No voice recordings, images, or identifiable user information are sent externally.

In addition, the system avoids over-automation by delivering assistance only when triggered by the user or clearly justified by safety context, minimizing the risk of over-reliance or intrusive prompting.

3 Experiment Description

To test the effectiveness of the system we designed an experiment consisting of a qualitative and a quantitative part. For this, five participants have been given the task to perform the four tasks of *making a cup of water*, *making a cup of tea*, *cooking pasta*, and *cooking rice* using the Aria glasses. After they performed all tasks they were first given a list of ten statements which they could rate from 1 to 5, and comment on their reasons for each rating. The rating scale can be seen in Table 2.

Rating	Meaning
1	The statement is never or almost never true in your experience.
2	The statement is rarely true.
3	The statement is sometimes true—about half the time.
4	The statement is usually true.
5	The statement is always or almost always true for you.

Table 2. Meaning of the rating scale.

After rating these statements, the participants are asked to answer five yes/no questions.²

Lastly, participants get the opportunity to give free feedback without any restrictions. These three parts represent the qualitative part of the experiment and aim to get a general idea about the practical usability of the whole system.

After that, the recordings of the four tasks for each participant are analysed to get a quantitative idea of how well the different parts work. For this, the positive and negative instances for five different parts of the system are counted: *Recognized Items*, *Stove State*, *Faucet State*, *Gaze Target*, and *Item Directions*.

4 Results and Discussion

The performance of the system was evaluated through both quantitative component analysis, and a small-scale user study involving five participants completing four predefined kitchen tasks: *making a cup of water*, *making a cup of tea*, *cooking pasta*, and *cooking rice*.

4.1 Model Performance

The fine-tuned YOLOv8n model achieved a mean average precision (mAP)_{@50} of 0.9175 and mAP_{@50:95} of 0.5598 on the test set, demonstrating strong detection performance on a limited, domain-specific dataset. Underrepresented classes trailed slightly in comparison.

Aside from this the model for faucet state detection also demonstrated a strong detection performance given the limited training data. For the class *faucet* it has a Precision of 0.91, Recall of 0.75 and F1-Score of 0.82. For *noise* on the other hand it has a Precision of 0.83, Recall of 0.94 and F1-Score of 0.88

In terms of system responsiveness, the entire pipeline, including object detection, gaze estimation, and suggestion generation, runs in real time on a consumer-grade laptop (Subsection 2.1). The RGB video pipeline, including object detection, operates at 10 frames per second (FPS), and the eye gaze estimation module also runs at 10 FPS. The average response time of the LLM, accessed via the GPT-4o-mini API, remains under one second per query, depending on the length of the input and output. This supports fluent interaction in typical kitchen scenarios without requiring specialized computing resources.

4.2 Experimental Evaluation

To assess real-world usability, five participants (1 female, 4 male; age: 20-30) completed all four kitchen tasks using the system. Their interactions were recorded and analysed both quantitatively, and qualitatively. All of them consented to this, were healthy and did not report any stress. In total more than 70 minutes of video material have been recorded during this study.³

² Statements: <https://github.com/lokrau/GLAMICA/tree/main/experiment>

³ Feedback forms for all experiments: <https://github.com/lokrau/GLAMICA/tree/main/experiment>

Quantitative Task Analysis An analysis of the task recordings shows that all parts of the system besides the stove state recognition were reasonably accurate across all tasks and participants. The different parts had the following accuracies: *Recognized Items*, 93.97%; *Stove State*, 55.68%; *Faucet State*, 86.36%; *Gaze Target*, 91.89%; *Item Direction*, 75.38%.

These results suggest that the multimodal fusion approach provides a reliable basis to generate context-aware guidance, even though some parts of the system, especially the *Stove State*, need more refinement to work satisfactorily.

Participant Ratings The participants rated ten system usability statements on a 5-point scale. The overall average rating of all the statements was 4.22, showing that the system was well perceived by the participants (see Table 2). Overall there were no statements that got a worse average rating than 3 and only three statements got a worse average rating than 4. These three statements are: *The system helped me remember what to do next.*, *The system made me more aware of potential risks (e.g., leaving the stove or faucet on).*, and *The system worked reliably throughout the tasks.*

The first statement received this rating because the system does not sense which instruction step the user is currently in. Because of this the user must inform the system of the last completed step for it to generate appropriate next steps. The second statement mainly received this rating because the *Stove State* is not detected satisfactory which aligns with the findings from the quantitative analysis. The last statement received this rating partially because of the deficits in the *Stove State* recognition and because the system’s answers were occasionally unhelpful.

On the other hand the two statements *The system correctly identified what I was looking at.*, and *The system was easy to use and understand.* are rated with a perfect 5 on average. For the first statement this aligns with the findings from the quantitative analysis were the *Gaze Target* and *Recognized Items* both have an accuracy of over 90%. For the second statement this outlines that the system is really easy to get used to, which is important for use with dementia patients.

Binary Feedback The yes/no questions further support these findings. All participants got used to the system quickly. Only one participant stated that the system was sometimes distracting or confusing. One trend that shows is that participants would not state that the system helps completing a task more efficiently, but it reduces the mental strain. Furthermore, one participant stated that the instructions were not always precise enough since they did not take into account the step the user is currently at in the cooking process.

4.3 Discussion

The experimental results demonstrate that the system is capable of supporting real-time, context-aware assistance in kitchen environments using consumer-grade hardware. The high mAP scores of the YOLOv8n model and strong performance of the faucet state classifier confirm the effectiveness of the visual and

sound based recognition components, even when trained on a relatively limited dataset. The use of temporal consistency (requiring detection over multiple frames) proved beneficial in reducing false positives, a common challenge in ego-centric video processing.

In real-world tasks, the system achieved high accuracy across most detection categories, with especially strong performance in identifying items and faucet states. However, item direction estimation showed comparatively lower accuracy, suggesting that errors in the readings of the IMU data still pose challenges. Furthermore, it showed that the simple rule-based stove state classification is performing too poorly for use in this scenario.

User feedback was generally positive, indicating good usability, and acceptance of the system. Participants particularly appreciated the system’s ease of use, the good item identification and that it is not intrusive. However, the lower ratings related to task efficiency and occasional confusion in system responses highlight the need for more adaptive and context-sensitive guidance generation, especially in longer, or multi-step tasks. Overall, the results indicate the feasibility of a lightweight, gaze-aware assistance system in domestic scenarios.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper introduced a portable, gaze-aware kitchen assistance system designed to support individuals with dementia in performing daily tasks. Built on the Project Aria glasses, it combines object detection, inertial tracking, gaze estimation, LLM-based instruction generation, and action recognition to provide real-time, context-sensitive guidance without requiring fixed instrumentation.

A lightweight YOLOv8n model was fine-tuned on a custom dataset to detect key kitchen objects with high accuracy. Persistent object awareness is achieved through IMU-driven rotation tracking, enabling the system to infer spatial context even when objects leave the user’s field of view. Detected items are structured into a KG, which constrains the LLM to generate personalised and feasible task suggestions. The LLM also receives information about the user’s gaze target, allowing it to generate explanations about specific objects without requiring the user to name them. Additionally, a simple action recognition module monitors stove and faucet interactions and issues safety reminders.

While our approach indicates the feasibility of real-time assistance in unstructured indoor environments using smart glasses, the current system still operates with a limited set of object classes and has only been evaluated in controlled settings with healthy participants. Future work will therefore expand the object vocabulary, improve spatial localisation through more advanced multimodal fusion, and strengthen action recognition to more accurately detect stove states and infer the user’s current step in the task. In addition, comprehensive studies with individuals experiencing cognitive impairments are needed to assess real-world usability, task adherence, and overall assistive impact.

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